

PUSKAPA
CENTER ON CHILD PROTECTION & WELLBEING

#A Fair Chance For All Children

A Guide to Researching with Young Women

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Glossary

Agency The ability to act independently and make one's own choices

Anonymous A condition in which a person's identity is kept confidential

Exploitative Actions that unfairly or harmfully take advantage of others

Inclusive Open and involving all parties

Intersectionality The overlapping of multiple identities held by an individual

Collaborative Cooperation between two or more parties to achieve a shared goal

Research Collaborator An individual who collaborates and is involved actively in a research project

Research Object The main target or focus of a study, which may include individuals, groups, events, or social phenomena.

UN United Nations

Taboo Something considered forbidden, inappropriate, or not to be discussed or done

UNESCO United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization

UNFPA United Nations Population Fund

A Love Letter from the Authors

Hi, readers!

Welcome and thank you for taking the time to read this guide.

We have compiled this guide as a token of our love for those of you who are about to conduct research, and also for you, the young women who may be researching, interested in, or even involved in a research journey!

For You, the Researchers

Before we set sail, it's important for you to know: **research isn't just a process of finding data or collecting stories, okay?**

Research can be a sensitive, meaningful meeting place, a point of connection for those in need. But, sometimes, whether consciously or unconsciously, research can become an exploitative space if you're not careful. Good research isn't just about 'taking' but about 'growing together' in the process.

This booklet is here as a guide and your friend before starting your research.

We invite you to conduct research in a warmer, more caring way: one that fosters sensitivity between researchers and participants, encourages collaboration, and creates meaningful engagement, so that those you involve in your research feel truly seen and respected throughout the process.

Remember! The people you are researching are not merely research objects. They are subjects, human beings with voices, opinions, feelings, experiences, needs, vulnerabilities, and choices.

For You, Young Women

who may be researching, interested, or even involved in a research journey.

We want to say, **you are important.**

Your voice, your opinions, your feelings, your experiences, your needs, your vulnerabilities, and your choices. All of these things have value beyond measure, and they are what make you, you.

Therefore, if the research doesn't feel right, if it's too exhausting or overwhelming, doesn't address your needs, or fails to accommodate your vulnerabilities, you have every right to voice this to the researcher.

Listen to the voice of your heart, mind, and body. Engage if you want to, share if you wish, and keep things private if you don't feel safe yet. Remember that because you are important, you have and are always entitled to a choice!

If you have been involved in research, we know exactly what it feels like; sometimes it's not easy being a woman. We often have so many conditions that make one or other things more complicated. Our experiences aren't always full of laughter; sometimes they are filled with fear, anxiety, hurt, and so many other feelings that just linger. Let's embrace them together as a part of ourselves, no matter how big or heavy they are.

Know that you are not alone; you have us and other young women who, even though separated by distance and time from you, are connected by similar experiences. Because of our circumstances, we are certainly allowed to ask to be understood and considered.

Finally, this guide exists to create a safe and free research space. Not just in writing, but one that is real and felt by researchers and research collaborators, which is not limited to young women.

Together, let's create research that is fair, equal, inclusive, full of empathy, and empowering.

With love,

**Fitriyatun Nisa, Manzilina Sorfina, Riza Dian, Tri Febi Maharani,
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Getting to Know Young Women

Who Are Young Women?

Understanding who young women are can help break taboos or feelings of discomfort surrounding certain topics, so that discussions and the research process can be more open, accepting, and comfortable.

When asked who we actually refer to as young women, many of us might immediately think of youth as a category defined by age. But is the category of young women only limited to that construction?

When seen from an age-based perspective, a woman may identify herself as young within the following age ranges:

- 15–24 years old → This is the United Nations' (UNESCO & UNFPA) definition of youth. However, this definition cannot be used as a universal standard, as each country defines it differently. The Indonesian government also sometimes uses this definition.
- 15–30 years old → A more flexible definition of youth used in some social research and activism in Indonesia, as it takes into account factors such as education, economic conditions, and social maturity.

But if we view it through an intersectional lens¹, young women can also be defined as **individuals who identify as women**, are in a transitional phase from adolescence to young adulthood, and face specific challenges due to a combination of factors such as age, gender, social class, access to education, disability, ethnicity, religion, and many others. Young women may be students, activists, labourers, religious school students (santri), unemployed, young mothers, or young women with disabilities.

When it comes to research, we need to see young women not merely as 'subjects' or sources of data, but as agents who actively shape the meaning of every research process they go through, bringing with them unique experiences of the body, emotions, power relations, and visions for the future. Young women are collaborative research partners.

Their characteristics cannot be generalised, but one thing is clear: young women are sensitive to their surroundings, have voices, and possess unique and authentic ways of expressing their experiences.

¹ For a more detailed explanation, see the discussion on intersectionality in this booklet.

Why Do Researchers Need to Understand Who Young Women Are?

The category of 'young women' is often overlooked or oversimplified, and as a result, they are not given space to speak for themselves, make their own decisions, or view the world in their own way.

Yet young women are in a critical phase of life, one that shapes their future direction, and they need support for their thoughts and perspectives, which are never the same from one young woman to another. Every young woman deserves to be treated in ways that are responsive to her needs and that prioritise her wellbeing.

That's why researchers need to first get to know young women, not just their names and ages, but also the world they feel and think through.

If researchers are able to understand the dynamics of young women's contexts, the research journey can become more flexible, connected, and comfortable. Building familiarity is key: it allows researchers to genuinely connect with collaborators, ensuring the process and outcomes truly reflect the voices of young women, rather than the researcher's assumptions.

Our hope, as the authors, is that the knowledge and experiences of young women can stand as an autonomous source of understanding: independent and self-defined, not reliant on others to be seen or validated.

Understanding Young Women in Indonesia: Unpacking Intersectionality

What is Intersectionality?

Why is Intersectionality Important in Research?

Intersectionality refers to the overlap of multiple identities held by an individual.

Gender, age, social class, ethnicity, religion, disability, sexual orientation, and other life experiences all intersect and shape how we, as young women, navigate the world on a daily basis. Intersectionality helps us understand that not all young women experience the world in the same way.

In research, it is essential to recognise this so that the process does not generalise the experiences of all young women.

Young women live in widely varied circumstances. For example, the experience of a young woman with a disability from a low-income background is certainly different from that of a middle-class young woman living in an urban area.

By understanding intersectionality, you as a researcher can design approaches that are more accommodating, inclusive, and sensitive to the diversity of lived experiences. It is crucial to see young women not merely as objects of study, but as subjects of knowledge, bringing their own unique perspectives shaped by their experiences.

Disclaimer:

Through the lens of intersectionality, women hold multiple identities at once. These overlapping identities place women in different positions of vulnerability. No single identity or condition is more important than another. They are all interconnected and collectively shape a person's lived experience.

Intersectionality of Young Women in Indonesia

Disability

If you're not yet familiar with the term 'disability', you may still carry certain stigmas toward young women with disabilities. These young women are often labelled with hurtful terms such as 'crippled', 'incapable', 'insane', 'stupid', 'weak', and other degrading labels. Disability often leads to marginalisation, making the voices of young women with disabilities rarely heard in everyday conversations. The discrimination faced by young women with disabilities is often not immediately visible. Researchers need to make the effort to learn about young women with disabilities, ensure they use affirming language, provide clear and accessible instructions and accommodations, learn proper helping ethics, and always be sensitive and proactive in interactions.

Religion

Religion is one of the key identities in Indonesian society. As a result, it also creates unequal political and power relations within social structures and norms. This condition often leads to discrimination against young women from religious minority groups, who are frequently labelled as 'deviant', judged harshly, and given very limited safe spaces to practise their faith. As a researcher, you must be aware of and respect the dynamics of majority–minority religious relations. Approach these differences with wisdom and avoid reactive behaviour throughout the research process.

Gender and Sexuality

Researchers need to understand the differences between gender and sexuality, recognise the diversity of gender identities, and ensure the presence of safe spaces. Variations in gender and sexual identity among young women often lead to stigma and labelling, which can cause discomfort and even trigger violence. Therefore, researchers must ensure that the needs and safety of young women with diverse gender and sexual identities are protected throughout the research process.

Sexual and Reproductive Health Rights

Young women are often stigmatised when accessing sexual and reproductive health services, such as STI testing or abortion. Sexuality is treated as a taboo topic, and research often reproduces these biases, portraying us as 'guilty' or 'immoral'. This approach overlooks our rights and needs, and reinforces symbolic violence. Researchers must not be judgmental and should respect our agency as individuals with lived experience.

HIV/AIDS

Young women living with HIV/AIDS often face stigma, discrimination, and threats to their privacy. In reality, most young women with this health condition were infected through circumstances beyond their control: sexual violence, transmission from a partner, or being born with it (as mothers with HIV can pass the virus to their children). In a research context, it is crucial that researchers do not reproduce blame-based narratives or position young women solely as victims.

Specific Health Conditions: Tuberculosis (TB) and Hepatitis

Young women with infectious diseases such as TB or hepatitis often face stigma that worsens their social isolation. Researchers need to understand that young women with specific health conditions also have the right to health and comfort. Ask what they need, ensure they are in good health and willing to participate, and provide space for rest when necessary. Health must be a priority, not something sacrificed for the sake of data.

Race and Ethnicity

Young women situated at the intersection of race and ethnicity often face discrimination, especially those from minority ethnic groups. This identity affects their access to education, healthcare, and social participation, as well as their representation in policy and public discourse. Researchers must be sensitive to the social, cultural, and historical contexts that may influence participation. Young women should never be treated merely as objects, especially when they come from communities that have historically experienced marginalisation.

Indigenous Communities

Young Indigenous women often live in close connection with environments that continue to uphold traditional customs in a harmonious way. Customary laws guide daily life, including gendered roles in work and responsibilities. Unfortunately, the voices of young Indigenous women are often overlooked, leaving them with little opportunity to speak or be heard. Researchers should consider using local languages or culturally appropriate forms of communication, respect social boundaries, such as how to speak with traditional leaders, and avoid topics considered taboo within the community. It is essential to ensure that the research setting and approach are safe and comfortable, free from coercion, whether direct or through local authorities. Researchers are also encouraged to create space for young Indigenous women to voice their perspectives and actively participate in the research process.

Class

Social class categorises individuals based on their economic situation. This affects how young women access various aspects of life. Many young women from lower social classes are often perceived as incapable, uneducated, or unworthy of friendship, among other stereotypes. Young women from the middle class often find themselves 'in between', making it difficult to find peers with similar experiences or to access support that matches their financial capacity. Young women from upper classes are frequently assigned positive labels such as 'smart', 'charming', or 'elegant', and often have broader access to resources, but they also face heavier social expectations and pressures. Rather than creating division or discrimination, differences in social class should encourage solidarity across classes. Terms like 'new rich', 'crazy rich', 'old money', or 'new middle class' only serve to reinforce unnecessary class stigma.

Education

Young women come from diverse educational backgrounds, which can lead to disparities in understanding. This can sometimes result in discomfort. Researchers must not assume that all young women share the same level of comprehension. It is important to ensure that each young woman has access to information and understanding that aligns with her specific needs.

Marital Status

When people hear the term young women, they often assume it refers only to those who are unmarried. In reality, young women come from a wide range of backgrounds. Some may already be married or even divorced. Researchers must not overlook this diversity. It is important to clarify which backgrounds are relevant for the research, as different backgrounds naturally come with different needs.

Young Women Experiencing Homelessness or in Alternative Living Arrangements

Young women experiencing homelessness or in alternative living arrangements are often stigmatised as 'troubled' or a 'social burden'. In truth, living in such conditions reflects a story of survival. In research, young women must be seen as whole individuals, not as objects of pity. Researchers should build relationships based on equality, recognising that the lived experiences of young women are sources of strength. Research should be a space for growth.

Children in Conflict with the Law (CICL)

Children in conflict with the law (CICL) are those involved in legal proceedings, whether as perpetrators, victims, or witnesses of a criminal offence. These children often face layered discrimination throughout the legal process: during investigation, prosecution, trial, sentencing, rehabilitation, and even after the legal process concludes. Girls in this category are especially vulnerable to stigma, often labelled as 'troublemakers', 'delinquents', or 'bad kids', which affects their social dynamics and makes it harder for them to access healthier environments. Researchers must ensure that such stigma is not reproduced during the research process.

Workers/Labourers

Young women workers often bear a double burden: working outside the home while still expected to fulfil domestic roles. As a result, they frequently face power imbalances and inequality in the workplace, along with restrictive social norms. This situation exposes women workers to stigma and discrimination, being seen as less competent, only suited for manual labour, unfairly paid, judged as failing to live up to gendered expectations, or even dismissed for being pregnant. Safe spaces for women workers to speak up about their rights and seek protection are often limited or entirely lacking. For example, domestic workers' unions in Indonesia are still fighting for their basic demands to be recognised. Researchers must ensure a safe environment and flexible timing for women workers participating in the research process.

Violence

Young women face vulnerabilities in many areas of life, including the risk of experiencing violence in any form. It is essential that their experiences and needs are carefully considered at every stage of the research process. Young women who have experienced violence, whether as victims or survivors, carry traumatic memories that may deeply affect them. Researchers must ensure that what is said or asked during the research process does not unintentionally trigger those memories or retraumatise participants.

Rural and Urban Areas

Young women living in urban areas often have greater access to resources but are accustomed to a faster-paced, more individualistic lifestyle. As a result, urban young women are frequently stigmatised as 'arrogant', 'unwilling to socialise', 'indifferent', 'spoiled', or 'classist'. In contrast, young women in rural areas often face limited access to education, economic opportunities, and infrastructure. They are more likely to be pressured into early marriage, and their voices are often excluded from decision-making, both within families and in broader community settings. Researchers must ensure that young women feel heard, seen, and valued, regardless of where they come from or what their background may be.

Sex Workers

Young women sex workers are frequently subjected to stigma and harmful labelling, which makes their safety especially vulnerable. Researchers must ensure the safety and privacy of young women sex workers, including their physical, digital, identity-related, social, health, and environmental security. A lack of care or sensitivity from researchers toward their experiences can have serious and lasting consequences for their lives.

Migrants

Many migrant women are often looked down upon and negatively labelled as 'promiscuous' or 'easily deceived', which leads to prejudice and unfair treatment from society. Young women with limited education are especially vulnerable to exploitative and potentially illegal recruitment processes. They not only face heavy workloads but also social pressure that frames them, for example, as carriers of disease or sources of social problems. These conditions reinforce harmful stereotypes against migrant women, severely limiting their access to safe spaces and the recognition of their rights. In research, it is important to challenge these negative generalisations and acknowledge the immense efforts migrant women make to support their families, while also facing significant risks of violence and harassment in the workplace.

Asylum Seekers

Research must create space for young women asylum seekers to share their experiences without pressuring them to disclose trauma they are not ready to speak about. Researchers should ensure that the research process supports healing and safety, and avoids reproducing discriminatory narratives. It is also essential to respect the language and cultural background of asylum seekers. If the researcher does not share the same language, they must arrange for a translator to help ensure the research process feels safe and comfortable.

Victims of National Strategic Projects (PSN)

In Indonesia, National Strategic Projects (PSN) are expanding rapidly; for example, infrastructure development in the Nusantara Capital City (IKN) area or forced evictions and relocations around the Mandalika Circuit. Land eviction also means the eviction of a decent life for local young women. Young women's existence is often overlooked, leaving no one to recognise how difficult the adaptation process can be. Researchers must be sensitive to the experiences of young women, especially those that are traumatic or marked by marginalisation. It is important to be aware that these difficult experiences may trigger trauma. Researchers must be able to recognise signs of distress and respond with empathy and care.

Victims of the 1965 Political Violence

Young women from families affected by the 1965 political violence in Indonesia carry the burden of inherited stigma: that their families belonged to traitorous, violent political groups. In reality, these families were victims of state-led violence and mass killings. Access to education and employment has been extremely difficult for children of those labelled as political enemies. Some have even had special markings on their ID cards. This political wound continues to shape the lives of many young women today. Insensitive research can reopen trauma or reinforce harmful stereotypes. It is therefore essential to ensure safety, respect confidentiality, and allow young women to retain control over their narratives. The courage of young women from these families to share their stories in research is a choice, not an obligation. Research must take the side of justice, not simply reproduce marginalising histories.

Core Principles of Researching with Young Women

Researching with young women is not just about collecting data: it's about building spaces that are safe, equal, and allow us to grow together.

We bring unique experiences and critical energy, so the research process needs to be engaging, safe, and built on mutual trust.

The core principle? No one is 'just an object' in the process. Everyone plays an important role. In the planning stages, **researchers need to design studies that involve young women as meaningful collaborators whose voices truly matter.** So let's shift our approach: from 'researching about' to 'researching with' young women!

This guide is here to support researchers in creating more effective and inclusive research processes. What follows are key principles you'll need to consider as a researcher.

Active and Meaningful Participation

Researchers should involve young women at every stage of the research process: from design and implementation to analysis and dissemination. Young women are not merely subjects; they are collaborators who play a vital role in your research.

During the process, some participants may be more active while others are more reserved. In this case, researchers must have strategies in place to ensure that all participants are engaged actively and equitably.

Researchers must remain neutral and not show favouritism toward any individual or group. Create an environment that encourages all participants to speak up.

There may be moments in your research when the responses or results don't match your expectations. In such situations, researchers must not lead or pressure participants to give certain answers.

Also be mindful to avoid asking questions that carry assumptions. As much as possible, use open-ended questions.

Equality and Inclusivity

- Researchers must be able to create a space that is free, inclusive, and equal for young women from diverse educational backgrounds, levels of knowledge, and perspectives, without discrimination. In an equitable space, the researcher is no longer the sole expert, but a facilitator in a shared process of learning and growth.
- Young women want their local knowledge and lived experiences to be respected and recognised, whether in academic or non-academic forms. Their knowledge is valuable, and their experiences should be treated as an equal source of insight.
- But recognition alone is not enough: the voices and experiences of young women must be represented authentically, without distortion. Researchers must ensure they are not giving undue attention to just one or two participants who appear more active or likeable. Instead, they should foster an environment where young women feel welcomed and valued, even if they don't have all the answers or hold different views from others.

Safety and Ethics

Throughout the research process, there may be moments that feel unsafe or uncomfortable for young women. That's why it is essential for researchers to consistently check in, ask for consent, and ensure the ongoing willingness of each young woman participating as a collaborator.

Before starting any research activities, make sure all collaborators are aware of each other's involvement so they can collectively build a commitment to mutual respect and protection.

Researchers must ensure that everyone involved in the study is committed to causing no harm: physically, mentally, sexually, or emotionally. It is also the researcher's responsibility to uphold the privacy, confidentiality, and rights of young women throughout the entire process.

The research must guarantee both physical and emotional safety. This includes providing informed consent that is easy to understand, given in stages, and accompanied by referrals if trauma surfaces. Researchers are also expected to provide information on support services and reporting channels from the outset, in case participants witness or experience violence.

Friendly and Accessible

Use language, methods, and analytical tools that are easy for young women to understand.

Clear and respectful communication is key to creating a relaxed and enjoyable research environment. Avoid overly academic language, don't corner participants with questions, and refrain from being judgemental.

Beyond communication, the methods and tools used in research should be presented in a simple, easy-to-understand format, and must be accessible to young women from diverse backgrounds.

Researchers are also expected to respond to specific situations or needs raised by young women collaborators, as some may face particular challenges, such as different communication styles or local language backgrounds. Avoid excessive technical jargon unless it is necessary and can be clearly explained.

Building Sensitivity and Connection

- Researchers need to recognise young women holistically by making collaborators feel seen, heard, and valued.
- In some situations, there may be collaborators who are quiet or passive. In such cases, researchers should create more space for them to speak. Conversely, if a collaborator tends to dominate the conversation, researchers should gently encourage them to make room for others to share their views.
- It is essential for researchers to understand the backgrounds of collaborators, who may come from diverse social, cultural, and geographical contexts. Every perspective carries its own story and experience, so a sensitive approach to diversity must be prioritised. This will help foster openness, trust, and active participation throughout the research process.
- Researchers should also build positive rapport while maintaining clear boundaries, respecting each collaborator's privacy and limits so they feel comfortable and at ease. It is equally important to listen to and affirm young women actively and empathetically throughout the research process.

Gender and Intersectionality-Informed Perspective

- It is essential for researchers to study and understand the intersectionality¹ of young women.
- Taking into account collaborators' identities, such as gender, disability, and socio-economic background, will help researchers design research approaches, methods, and analyses that are appropriate and responsive to each collaborator. Layered identities (such as class, race, disability, sexual orientation, and more) shape young women's experiences, access to opportunities, and the ways their voices are heard.

Needs-Based Approach

Design your research based on real needs that are identified together with young women.

Understanding the specific needs of young women will help generate research data that is fair, representative, and relevant. To create an engaging research experience, researchers can use methods, media, and language that young women understand, including visual, audio, or other creative strategies.

Before conducting the research, researchers must prepare the information to be shared. This includes clearly explaining the purpose and potential risks of the research in accessible language, as well as providing information on where and how to report if any violence occurs during the research process.

Empowerment

- Research should serve as a tool to strengthen the capacity and confidence of young women.
- The outcomes of the research should not stop at written reports, they should be returned to young women and their communities in accessible formats, such as policy recommendations, follow-up training, or new tools and methods that can support future research.
- Researchers are encouraged not to demand immediate or short-term results from collaborators. Instead, they should approach the process with care and patience, respecting each young woman's journey in understanding and sharing the information the research requires.
- Always remind collaborators that they are free to withdraw at any time and are never obligated to answer every question posed by the researcher.

¹ For a more detailed explanation, see the discussion on intersectionality in this booklet.

Let's Play!

A Checklist for Your Readiness to Conduct Research with Young Women

After understanding the core principles of researching with young women, researchers now need to prepare the essential documents required for involving young women in the research process.

These documents are not only important for the young women participating as collaborators, but also for the researchers themselves, to ensure the research process runs smoothly and follows clear procedures.

A note for young women:

You have the right to request these important documents from the researcher. If you find that the values in the research don't align with yours, you are free to choose not to participate. Even if you've already started the research process, you still have the right to withdraw at any time if you feel uncomfortable.

Let's check your readiness before involving young women in your research. The contents of the documents below can be combined or kept separate. What matters is that you provide all the necessary information.

Once you've prepared each item, feel free to tick it off!

You've prepared a document that outlines your research, including the background and timeline, for the young women collaborators involved.

Tick here if available →

A note for young women:

This document is important for helping you understand how the research you're involved in may impact you. It's also essential to know the research timeline so you can consider how it fits with your own schedule.

You've prepared an **informed consent document** for the young women who will be involved in the research. This document clearly states that their participation is entirely voluntary, that they are free to decline involvement, and that they may withdraw at any time without pressure or consequences.

Tick here if available →

In the informed consent document, it's also important to clearly state the rights of young women throughout their participation in the research, as well as any potential risks or consequences that may arise as a result of the research.

You should also explain how the information gathered will be shared, documented, and used.

Additionally, the informed consent form should include a section that acknowledges the intersectional identities of young women. Give them the freedom to express their specific circumstances and needs related to their intersectional experiences.

A note for young women:

This document is important for you to formally state your participation. Remember: you have full authority to decline. Your comfort and safety come first. You are also free to share, or not share, anything about your intersectional identity. If you feel that doing so could put you at risk, you have every right to withhold that information. However, if there are specific conditions or needs you would like the researcher to be aware of, don't hesitate to write them down and ask for support.

You've prepared a **document that outlines the values you uphold in the research.**

Tick here if available →

For example, you might state that you are committed to values such as inclusivity, respecting everyone's opinions, and maintaining confidentiality throughout the research process. But remember: this isn't just a document or a written statement. It's your responsibility to actively ensure that young women collaborators are in a space where they feel free and safe to express their views!

A note for young women:

If there are any values in the research that don't align with your own views, you are absolutely allowed to ask questions or choose not to participate.

You've prepared a **document that outlines your commitment to preventing all forms of violence, includes a clear reporting pathway in case violence occurs, and explains the procedures for handling such cases.**

Centang disini bila ada →

A note for young women:

Make sure this document is available and that there is a clear commitment from the researcher. Your safety and wellbeing must be fully supported in any research you take part in. You also have the right to ask further questions about the technical details, such as what services will be provided if you experience sexual violence, what kind of assistance you'll receive, and how the reporting and support process will work. Don't hesitate to access these services when you need them.

So, have you ticked all the boxes?

If you have, that means you're one step closer to being ready to conduct research with young women. But if not, take the time to prepare the documents listed above to ensure their involvement is free from exploitation and harm. And remember: this isn't just about ticking boxes or putting things in writing. It's a commitment that must be actively created, nurtured, and upheld throughout the entire research process.

Let's Play!

How Affirmative and Inclusive is Your Research in Engaging Young Women?

Now let's take a look: how inclusive is your research when it comes to involving young women?

Let's start!

Checkpoint 1: **Communication and Knowledge Exchange**

- You've created a two-way communication space with young women collaborators, not just one-way from researcher to participant.
- You've asked how young women understand the research topic, rather than making assumptions.
- You've made space and ensured collaborators know they're welcome to ask questions and express curiosity about your research.
- You've provided reading materials, references, or explanations in language that is accessible and easy for young women to understand.
- You respect and record the opinions, local knowledge, and personal experiences of young women without judgement or dismissal.
- You've made it clear that there are no wrong answers when they participate.

Checkpoint 2: **Building Trust and Safety**

- You've created open communication that allows young women to share, or not share, information according to their comfort level.
- You've made it clear that they are free to use their real identity or remain anonymous.
- You're prepared to acknowledge and respect young women's diverse intersectional identities (e.g. disability, minority background, gender identity, and sexuality).
- You've ensured a safe space (physically, emotionally, and psychologically) for young women to collaborate.

Checkpoint 3: Ethical Awareness and Representation

- You've obtained informed consent, written and/or verbal, in a way that collaborators truly understand.
- You've discussed how the research findings will be used, and whether collaborators do or do not want their identity/experiences to be mentioned.
- You've given young women the opportunity to review and provide feedback on how their involvement is represented in the final report, along with a clear explanation of how their feedback will be incorporated (review rights).
- Informed consent is provided in a language that collaborators can understand.
- Collaborators are free to choose which aspects of their identity they wish to share.
- A safe space is available for collaborators to take breaks or withdraw from the process at any time, without pressure.

Checkpoint 4: Respecting Diversity

- As a researcher, you've made the effort to learn about diversity, especially if you're not yet familiar with it.
- Your research acknowledges and accommodates the needs of collaborators from a variety of backgrounds.

Wow, you're already halfway there! Let's keep going and see whether your research is truly inclusive and responsive to the diverse needs of young women.

Checkpoint 5: Ensuring Accessibility

- You've provided accommodations based on participants' needs (e.g. sign language interpreter, translator, transport, disability-friendly materials).
- Your research methods are flexible and adaptable to suit the situations of your collaborators.

Checkpoint 6: Positioning Young Women as Subjects with Knowledge

- Young women are genuinely listened to and recognised as key sources of knowledge.
- Young women are involved in shaping the form and direction of the research.
- Their stories are used in ways that honour their dignity.
- The research avoids exploiting their experiences for commercial, academic, or political gain.

FINISH: YAY! You've made it to the finish line!

Preparing for this kind of research is definitely not easy. But, don't worry, our intention in sharing all of this isn't to make things harder for you. In fact, it's the opposite: we want to help you prepare your research so that it's more thoughtful, inclusive, and meaningful!

A note for young women:

Remember, you are important! That's why you absolutely have the right to remind the researcher, especially after reading this guide and participating in a research project, if there's anything you need that hasn't been provided. You're also fully encouraged to add, adjust, remove, or revise any of the points above if they don't quite fit your needs.

A Reference List of Accessible Methods and Tools for Research Analysis

If you want to do research with young women, the analytical tools you use should be flexible, not rigid. Analysis isn't just about breaking down data; it's also about capturing emotion, context, and the meaning behind the words. That's why it's so important to use approaches that genuinely embrace our lived experiences in authentic ways.

These recommendations aren't just about sharing theory; they're here to offer tools that help both young women and researchers truly connect.

Ready to explore exciting analytical tools? Let's go!

Interactive Story Mapping

Purpose: We (young women) co-create a map of our life stories, our experiences and dreams, so they can be read, felt, and understood. It's not just about being heard, but about giving our voices direction and context. Through visuals, symbols, or words, researchers can begin to see our patterns, struggles, and strengths.

Format: Visuals, collages, drawings, or narrative cards. Can be made accessible with visual/audio tools for participants with visual impairments. Young women with intellectual disabilities can use simple symbols or images.

Flow: The interactive story mapping process begins by inviting young women to choose meaningful moments from their lives that they wish to share. These are then visualised in a story map, such as a timeline, diagram, or digital collage. Participants are given space to narrate the meaning of each moment through writing, audio, or images. The researcher then facilitates a participatory reflective discussion to explore emerging key themes. The final analysis is done collaboratively, ensuring that young women retain control over how their stories are interpreted.

Problem Tree / Hope Tree Analysis

Purpose: The tree analysis is created together, not just to identify problems, but also to collectively imagine what an ideal world looks like from young women's perspectives. From the roots of the problems to the branches of hope, we map it all out together! The goal is for our voices and experiences to not only be heard, but to guide change that's meaningful and connected to our dreams.

Format: Small group discussions, drawing a large tree on poster paper or using digital media. The researcher explains using simple, accessible language and provides a sign language interpreter if needed.

Flow: The researcher prepares a large tree image on paper or digital media, and guides the young women to fill in the tree with relevant content. For example, a problem tree is filled with challenges faced by young women in different areas of life, while a **hope tree** is filled with aspirations and solutions they envision in response to those challenges.

Digital Diary

Purpose: This tool creates a safe space for sharing, especially for things that are hard to say out loud but important to express. Through this space, we (young women) have control over our stories and how we want to tell them. What's more, it becomes a channel for reflection, because writing (or creating) helps us better understand ourselves and draw strength from our own stories.

Format: It doesn't need to be formal or academic. Participants can use text, images, voice notes, poetry, or anything that feels comfortable. Researchers should offer the option to remain anonymous for those who aren't ready to share their identity. Digital access must be considered, with offline alternatives provided if needed.

Flow: The digital diary process begins with a relaxed and clear introduction of the concept and purpose to participants. Young women are then invited to choose their preferred format, text, audio, visual, or video. They complete the diary independently over a certain period, guided by reflective prompts. Collected data is thematically organized without stripping away personal nuance. Researchers are encouraged to involve participants in interpreting the meaning, maintaining context, and ensuring data security. The final analysis should use a participatory approach that keeps the narrative authentic and rooted in the lived experiences of young women.

Intersectionality Reflection Cards (Narrative Card Sorting)

Purpose: This tool maps young women's identities and lived experiences by arranging narrative cards that reflect their life situations, privileges, challenges, and personal values. It can also be adapted to explore experiences of layered discrimination (such as those related to gender, age, disability, and more).

Format: Cards may contain prompts like 'I feel heard when...', 'I feel unsafe when...', or 'People see me as...'. These can be printed or used digitally through platforms like Google Slides or Miro.

Flow: Participants are invited to choose, arrange, and respond to the cards that best resonate with their own experiences.

Emotion Mapping

Purpose: To uncover young women's experiences by linking specific emotions to physical or social spaces where they feel safe, unheard, uncomfortable, or empowered. This tool helps connect inner experiences to physical environments and reveal spatial dynamics of power and vulnerability.

Format: Use a map of relevant spaces (e.g. school, pesantren, home, digital environments) and coloured stickers or symbols to represent different emotions. It can be simplified for participants with intellectual disabilities and adapted with audio descriptions for those with visual impairments.

Flow: Participants are invited to place colour-coded stickers or symbols on parts of the map that correspond with how they feel in those spaces. (Example: placing a red sticker on the 'home' area of the map to show feeling unsafe.)

Secret Box / Anonymous Story Box

Purpose: To provide a private, safe space for young women to write or draw about experiences that are difficult to express openly. This method helps uncover hidden realities while ensuring a sense of safety and confidentiality.

Format: A physical box placed in a community space or an anonymous online form. Can also be adapted into audio or symbolic formats. Especially suitable for sensitive topics such as violence or discrimination.

Flow: Participants can write or draw anything they wish to share without revealing their identity. The contents are not meant to be publicly displayed.

Games Using the Values Clarification for Actions and Transformation (VCAT) Method / Choose 'YES' or 'NO'

- **Purpose:** Allows researchers to observe each young woman collaborator's perspective and enables them to express their views freely without fear of judgment.
- **Format:** Present a statement (e.g. 'Women are weak'). Participants respond by choosing from clear options: either digitally or using two physical cards marked "YES" and "NO".
- **Flow:** Each collaborator selects their answer (agree/disagree or yes/no) independently, with no external input or commentary. Other participants are not allowed to comment on anyone's responses.

A Note for Researchers:

The methods listed here are simply references. They are options for engaging or enjoyable approaches. However, it's entirely possible that some young women may feel uncomfortable with these methods. If you, as the researcher, are familiar with other approaches, feel free to adapt them based on shared needs and comfort.

Support and Counselling Service Mechanisms

You Should Know!

Reading references and hotlines for organisations providing support in cases of violence.

Support and Counselling Service Mechanisms

During the research process, difficult stories or experiences may emerge, especially those related to violence or discomfort. That's why it's important for you to know: you are not alone.

If at any point during the research you need help, emotional support, or wish to report something, there are support and counselling services ready to assist you.

You can access and search for the services you need at carilayanan.com. This website provides many options, including the type of organisation you're looking for and a selection of services available in or near your area.

A Note for Researchers:

Make sure that the organisations listed on carilayanan.com are truly competent, uphold a survivor-centred perspective, and provide timely responses when accessed for support services.

Young Women, Here's Some Extra Info for You!

If you're wondering: 'Is there a specific reporting body for research-related issues, like when a researcher violates ethical codes or commits abuse?' The answer is: **Yes**. But **they are not always centralised or publicly accessible**. Reporting mechanisms often depend on the **researcher's institutional affiliation** or on the **organisation funding or publishing the research**.

Research Ethics Committees (Institutional Review Boards / IRB)

If a researcher comes from a university, NGO, or official institution, they are **required to obtain approval from a research ethics committee**.

You can submit a complaint to the ethics committee of their institution. For example:

- Research Ethics Committee of the Faculty of Psychology, Universitas Indonesia
- Ethics Committee of LIPI/BRIN
- Ethics Committees at hospitals/universities for studies related to health or humanitarian issues

TYou have the right to ask the researcher directly: 'Which ethics committee reviewed this research?' It's your right to know.

Funding Institutions or Program Partners

If the researcher is working on a grant-funded project (such as from UN Women, the Ford Foundation, or other international donors), they are usually required to implement **participant protection systems** and have **misconduct reporting procedures**.

Check the funder's website → there's usually buttons to 'Report Misconduct' or 'Safeguarding Concern'

Internal Services within Research Networks or Collectives

If the researcher is working under a civil society network or feminist collective, ask if they have:

- A grievance mechanism
- An ethics or internal complaints team

Example: Some feminist organisations have internal 'Safer Space' mechanisms to handle conflicts or violations.

LPSK or Komnas Perempuan (For serious cases of violence)

If the misconduct involves sexual violence, exploitation, or degrading treatment toward women, you can contact:

Komnas Perempuan (National Commission on Violence Against Women) → <https://komnasperempuan.go.id/>

LPSK (Witness and Victim Protection Agency) → <https://lpsk.go.id/>

Important Note:

For young women:

If you have your own reference or preference for support organisations or assistance services, you can absolutely communicate this to the researcher. You have the right to ask before or during the research: 'If I feel uncomfortable or experience harassment, where can I report it?'

For researchers:

You are required to inform participants about their rights, including the right to say no, withdraw, or report misconduct. You must also **verify and re-check all listed support services** to ensure they are still active and operate with a survivor-centred approach.

Closing: See You in Spaces Where We Grow Together

We wrote this booklet out of a shared belief that young women deserve to be at the centre of research, not just as objects, but as subjects in their own right.

We believe that research can be a safe, liberating, and nurturing space for learning and growth, if we commit to working on it together.

To you, the researcher seeking to involve young women: we hope this booklet serves as a reminder that the process matters. That listening, creating dialogue, and growing together are far more valuable than simply 'collecting data'.

If reading this has sparked any ideas, critique, or if you want to share your thoughts with us, **we warmly welcome your feedback!** Please fill in the feedback form at bit.ly/feedback-buklet or scan the QR code. Just like research, this booklet is also a space for growth, and we'd love to grow with you.

Thank you for learning and moving with us towards research that is more just, inclusive, and meaningful.

See you in collaborative spaces that are safer, fairer, and filled with care.

Warm hugs from all of us.

Fitriyatun Nisa

Manzilina Sorfina

Riza Dian

Tri Febi Maharani

Umi Nurdianti

Vallery Kendira Adelina Massardi

QR Code Feedback:

